

Microstrain and Urbach energy relaxation in FAPbI₃ based solar cells through powder engineering and perfluoroalkyl phosphate ionic liquid additive

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Abstract

The structural and electronic imperfections are the origin of the defects and lead to the non-radiative recombination that is detrimental to fabricate efficient perovskite solar cells (PSCs). Here we propose an innovative powder engineering method of employing pre-synthesized α -FAPbI₃ powder as a precursor material. Our developed methodology of α -FAPbI₃ powder mitigates the

notorious structural and electronic imperfections through a significant decline in the microstrain and Urbach energy as compared to reported δ -FAPbI₃ powder and conventional precursor methods. In addition to the performance enhancement in photovoltaics, our engineered powder showed remarkable thermal and moisture stability along with cost-effectiveness through the employment of low-grade PbI₂. Further, through additive engineering, with the use of ultra-hydrophobic perfluoroalkyl phosphate anion-based ionic liquid, the microstrain and Urbach energy were brought down to the lowest value of 1.67×10^{-4} and 12.47 meV respectively as a result of defect passivation and a semi-ionic F-Pb interaction that stabilizes the surface.

1. Introduction

Galvanized from the successful employment of metal halide perovskites as a dye in 2009¹ followed as a light harvester in 2012², significant research has been carried out during the last decade in the field of perovskite-based solar cells.³ From its initial days of research to probe methylammonium lead triiodide, currently emphasis has been shifted to formamidinium lead triiodide (FAPbI₃) based perovskites, which possess a lower optical bandgap (1.48 eV) close to Shockley–Queisser limit (1.34 eV) and higher stability.⁴⁻⁷ However, its adverse phase transition between photoactive (α -phase) and photo-inactive (δ -phase) phases constrain long-term stability at atmospheric conditions. Through the partial doping of FA and iodide sites (mixed perovskites), surface passivation, and additive engineering are collective ways to overcome the phase instability and defect formations,⁸⁻¹² the induced structural and optoelectronic disorders impede the photovoltaic (PV) reliability. Moreover, reports suggest partial doping or additive engineering with larger molecules can induce stress on the perovskite structure and thus produced microstrain impacts on structural stability, defects generation, and charge carrier dynamics.¹³⁻¹⁶ Variations in

the microstrain of the perovskite can create the disorder near the band edge. Thus, the qualitative analyses of structural and energetic disorder of perovskite can be estimated from the microstrain and Urbach energy calculations.^{17,18}

Reports suggest reduced defect density and improved stability in a single-crystalline perovskite when compared to polycrystalline.^{19,20} capitalizing this opportunity, research is being carried out to achieve defect-free FAPbI₃ based PSCs through precursor engineering. In this direction, pre-synthesized non-perovskite δ -FAPbI₃ powder as the precursor material was employed to fabricate reproducible PSCs.^{21,22} On comparing the performance between the δ -FAPbI₃ powder and α -FAPbI₃ powder as precursor material, authors noted α -FAPbI₃ prepared from 3-methoxypropionitrile lags behind the δ -FAPbI₃ in terms of PSC performances.²¹ Improved PCE of >21% was achieved from the δ -FAPbI₃ powder-based PSCs with the MAI additive, and the improved PCE was attributed to a 22% decrease in the defect density as compared to the conventional counterpart.²² Recently, >23% PCE for pre-synthesized α -FAPbI₃ powder-based PSCs with an octyl ammonium iodide passivation was reported, and the PCE was further improved to 25.6% with a formate anion treatment which suppresses the anion vacancies at the grain boundaries.³ The authors incorporated 35 mol% of MAI additive and the compositional analysis suggests the structural incorporation of 5% MA⁺ cation. It is worth noting that the FAPbI₃ based PSCs with >21% PCE is achieved by the incorporation of excess MAI, which comes with the notorious instability and bandgap widening. Thus the fabrication of MA-free FAPbI₃ based PSCs is of paramount importance.

On the other hand, ionic liquids (ILs) have emerged as a promising non-volatile additive in PSCs due to their hydrophobic nature, high chemical and thermal stability, low-temperature processability, and excellent electrochemical properties. The introduction of ILs has been reported

to assist in perovskite crystal growth, improving the crystallinity, modifying the surface defect, thus improve the open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and the stability against atmospheric stresses. However, most of the studies were focused on the cationic part of ILs and the imidazolium-based ILs with hexyl side chain have been investigated.²³⁻²⁶ In most cases, the anionic combinations have been limited to hexafluorophosphate (PF_6), tetrafluoroborate (BF_4), and halides which show limited hydrophobicity. The perfluoroalkyl phosphate (PAP) anion-based ILs possess ultra-hydrophobicity and improved thermal and electrochemical stability as compared to their PF_6 , BF_4 , and halide counterparts.²⁷ Hence, their exploitation in PSCs can be an effective strategy to fabricate long-term stable PSCs.

Here, we adopted a powder engineering methodology to synthesize an MA-free α -FAPbI₃ powder and its opto-electrical, structural, and PV properties were investigated and compared with the conventional and δ -FAPbI₃ powder processed absorber layers. We noted a drastic reduction in structural and energetic disorders for α -FAPbI₃ powder-based perovskites over the conventional and δ -FAPbI₃ powder. This in turn enhanced the phase stability and PV performances. We further employed two PAP-based ILs with ethyl and hexyl functionalized imidazolium cations, and the fabricated PSCs gave PCE over 18%. From the XPS analysis, we identified an F-Pb semi-ionic interaction that immobilizes the under-coordinated Pb atoms at the surface.

Moreover, the combination of hexyl-imidazolium cation and perfluoroalkyl phosphate anion gave enhanced thermal and shelf-life stability to promote retaining over 70% of initial PCE after 500 min of MPP tracking where the control device lost its 80% of initial PCE within 200 min.

Results and discussion:

Powder Engineering: We derived α -FAPbI₃ powder by annealing the as-synthesized δ -FAPbI₃ powder²¹ at 150 °C for 1 hour in an inert atmosphere (supporting information, SI). The perovskite

powders were synthesized from low-grade PbI_2 (99%, Sigma Aldrich) to reduce the cost.²⁸ The phase purity of synthesized α -FAPbI₃ powder has been identified by diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) techniques. The DRS spectrum was converted to the pseudo-absorption spectrum using the widely accepted Kubelka–Munk function $\{F(R)\}$ ²⁹ (Figure S1a) and, we derived the Tauc plot from the Kubelka–Munk transformed data and the estimated optical band gap is 1.47 eV (Figure 1a). The indexed diffractogram of α -FAPbI₃ powder (Figure S1b) suggests high phase purity.

Figure 1. a) Tauc plot estimated for α -FAPbI₃ powder from DRS spectra, digital image of synthesized α -FAPbI₃ is shown as the inset b) XRD diffractogram from PbI_2 , FAI, δ -FAPbI₃, and α -FAPbI₃ powders, c) UV-Vis absorption spectra, and d) diffractograms of conventional and powder engineered perovskite thin films.

Diffractograms of starting materials lead iodide (PbI_2), formamidine hydroiodide (FAI), and the δ -FAPbI₃, α -FAPbI₃ powders are represented in Figure 1b. α -FAPbI₃ powder showed no residual FAI which appeared in δ -FAPbI₃ powder (weak peak at 25.5°). The two weak peaks that appeared at $2\theta < 14^\circ$ for α -FAPbI₃ has attributed to the $K\beta$ and W lines originated from instrumental contaminations.

The deposition of high-quality perovskite film is the crucial step to achieve high performance. Here we have spin-coated the perovskite layers from δ -FAPbI₃ and α -FAPbI₃ powders and compared them to the well-established conventional method. For the conventional method, we dissolved commercial FAI and PbI_2 in DMF: DMSO solvent mixture, whereas the δ -FAPbI₃ and α -FAPbI₃ powder were dissolved in the solvent mixture to prepare the 1.4 M precursor solution, and the spin-coated thin films were annealed at 150°C for 20 minutes (min) to ensure the complete phase-conversion. Formamidine hydrochloride (FACl) was used as an additive in all the precursor solutions to stabilize the perovskite phase and to realize larger grains.³ The diffractograms of FACl added FAPbI₃ perovskite layers (Figure S2) suggest the induced crystallinity at an optimized 0.42 M FACl addition. The magnified view of the (100) plane shows no shifting in the peak and the UV-Vis absorption spectra (Figure S3) suggest a similar bandgap. Arguably, the chlorides (Cl^-) are smaller than iodides (I^-), and the incorporation of Cl^- in the perovskite structure may result in shifting of PXRD peaks and blue shifting of UV-Vis spectra. Notably, no changes in the spectra with FACl addition suggests the absence of Cl^- in the perovskite layers. Cl^- may leave the perovskite surface upon annealing due to its lower sublimation temperature.³⁰ To harmonize the terminology, hereafter, the perovskite layer deposited from the conventional method, δ -FAPbI₃, and α -FAPbI₃ powders were termed as c-FAPI, δ -FAPI, and α -FAPI respectively. To investigate the role of different precursor materials on the performance of PSCs, we decipher the

optoelectronic and structural properties. The UV-Vis absorption spectra are shown (Figure 1c), where α -FAPbI₃ showed the maximum absorption onset than of δ -FAPbI₃ and c-FAPbI₃ indicating the improved crystallinity. We further estimated the $\tau\alpha$ plots (Figure S4) and a similar bandgap of 1.49 eV were obtained for all three perovskites. A somewhat higher bandgap for the thin films can be attributed to the possible presence of multiple absorptions, reflections, and scattering in the thin film sample.³¹ The close examination of absorption onsets displays the sub-bandgap absorption edges for the three perovskites just below their band gaps which are known as the Urbach tails and characterized by the Urbach energy (E_U) in the literature³² where the absorption coefficient and the E_U are related by,

$$\alpha(E) = \alpha_0 \exp\left\{\frac{E-E_C}{E_U}\right\} \dots\dots\dots (I)$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, E_C and α_0 are constants, and E is the photon energy. The exponential relation between the absorption coefficient and the photon energy and the E_U has been calculated from the slope of the exponential decay of the absorption onset (Figure S5). α -FAPbI₃ registered the lowest E_U of 13.22 meV while the δ -FAPbI₃ and c-FAPbI₃ exhibited higher values of 15.99 meV and 19.32 meV respectively. A reduction in the E_U is significant as the E_U is a measure of energetic disorder at band edge and is known to impede the PV performance by reducing the diffusion length, carrier mobility, and the open-circuit voltage deficit.^{33,34} Additionally, Urbach tails indicate the presence of deep trap states which inhibit the device performance through non-radiative recombination. In this context, the synthesized α -FAPbI₃ with a lower E_U by 6.10 and 2.77 meV than of c-FAPbI₃ and δ -FAPbI₃ respectively, are a promising alternative for FAPbI₃ based PSCs. Diffractograms were recorded (Figure 1d) for all the three perovskites, no peak shifting was observed and the δ -phase was fully inhibited in all three cases, however, we noted the presence of unreacted PbI₂ in δ -FAPbI₃. Remarkably, the peak intensities increase substantially for α -FAPbI₃ and

δ -FAPbI₃ than for c-FAPbI₃ suggesting the enhanced crystallinity which is in agreement with the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs (Figure S8). We further quantified the microstrain using the Williamson-Hall (W-H) equation¹⁶,

$$\beta \cos \theta = \frac{k\lambda}{D} + 4\varepsilon \sin \theta \dots\dots\dots(\text{II})$$

where β, λ, k, D and ε denote the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of XRD peak, the wavelength of X-ray radiation, Scherrer constant, crystallite size, and the microstrain respectively. $\beta \cos \theta$ was plotted as a function of $4 \sin \theta$ and the corresponding slopes were estimated as the microstrains. The microstrain dropped from 5.16×10^{-4} to 3.16×10^{-4} for δ -FAPbI₃ as compared to c-FAPbI₃, (Figure 1f) and it shows further decrement to achieve the lowest value of 1.95×10^{-4} for the synthesized α -FAPbI₃ (Figure S6). We attribute the origin of the microstrain to the higher Goldschmidt tolerance factor ($t > 1$) of FAPbI₃ and thermal expansion coefficient gradient at the perovskite-substrate interface. We performed depth depended diffractograms for c-FAPbI₃ and α -FAPbI₃ thin films to unravel the crystal structure inhomogeneity, i.e., structural imperfections along with the perovskite thickness (detailed in the experimental section of supporting information). A gradual shift of diffraction peaks towards lower angles across the depths profile, suggests the crystal structure inhomogeneity along with the film thickness.^{15,35} We noted (Figure S7), reduced diffraction plane peak shifting (100) for α -FAPbI₃ than of c-FAPbI₃ pointing towards the versatility of our powder methodology that effectively mitigates the structural imperfections. The induced intrinsic and extrinsic strains can contribute to the phase transformation where the tensile strained α -FAPbI₃ quickly rearranges to the δ -FAPbI₃ as depicted schematically in Figure 1e.^{13,14} To acquire insights into the perovskite under different environmental stresses, we investigated the structural variation under thermal and moisture conditions. FAPbI₃ layers are reported to go through two degradation pathways, first the decomposition to PbI₂, and second, the perovskite can

undergo phase transition against the environmental stresses such as temperature, moisture, and light. The FAPbI₃ showed improved thermal stability as compared to the existing MAPbI₃-based PSCs, while it undergoes a faster phase transition to undesirable δ -phase. The degradations against the atmospheric stresses have been tracked with structural evaluations such as X-ray and neutron powder diffractions.^{36,37} The fabricated thin films were annealed at 85 °C for thermal stability test and kept at 45-50 % relative humidity (RH) at dark at room temperature for moisture stability test, and the corresponding diffractograms and digital photographs were documented over time (Figure S9-S11). The normalized diffractograms collected for the perovskite thin films before and after the thermal annealing at 85 °C for 500 hr (Figure S11) depicts, the decomposition of the perovskite phase to PbI₂ is visible for c-FAPI while the δ -FAPI and α -FAPI showed improved thermal stability by retaining the perovskite structure. Simultaneously, we tracked the influence of moisture and the corresponding photographs and diffractograms were exhibited (Figure S9 and S10). Upon moisture stress, c-FAPI showed a rapid conversion to δ -phase within 24 hr and almost full conversion was realized within 100 hr of exposure. Expectedly,^{21,22} δ -FAPI is more stable, however, the (010) (δ -phase) plane emerged after 24 hr, and further evolved with a significant presence after 100 hr. Notably, there was no sign of the presence of (010) plane after 24 hr for α -FAPI, suggesting improved phase stability. The emergence of this peak was only visible after 100 hr of exposure for α -FAPI. Remarkably, the intensity of (100) α -phase perovskite peak drastically drop-down for c-FAPI and recorded a significant decrease for δ -FAPI, but in the case of α -FAPI, it retained the intensity even after 100 hr moisture exposure. The powder-engineered induced tensile strain- relaxation effectively to stabilize the α -phase also at harsh conditions. Moreover, α -FAPI shows higher crystallinity and lowest Urbach energy which can translate to improve PV performances.

The PV parameters were collected from a PSC with a mesoscopic architecture of FTO/c-TiO₂/mp-TiO₂/Perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au (Figure 2a). Figure 2b depicts the current density–voltage (J - V) characteristics under AM 1.5G illumination (100 mW cm⁻²). The synthesized α -FAPI device gave a PCE of 16.37% with an open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of 962 mV, a short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) of 23.80 mA cm⁻² and a fill factor (FF) of 71.44%, whereas δ -FAPI and c-FAPI displayed a reduced PCEs of 16.09% (V_{OC} = 958 mV, J_{SC} = 23.63 and FF = 71.05%) and 15.93% (V_{OC} = 948 mV, J_{SC} = 23.42 and FF = 71.72%) respectively. The improved PCEs of powder-based α -FAPI was attributed to the enhancement in the V_{OC} and J_{SC} values. We ascribed the marginal increment in J_{SC} to the improved crystallinity which is evident from the structural and morphological analyses. Additionally, we observed the V_{OC} increased by 10 mV for δ -FAPI and 14 mV for α -FAPI than of conventional c-FAPI. As discussed in the earlier section, the decrease in the E_U value can boost the PV performance. Since J_{SC} is primarily dependent on the bandgap of thin-film absorber, E_U does not have any close relation with J_{SC} but it defines the $V_{OC,def}$ (i.e., the difference between bandgap and open-circuit voltage), and reduction in the E_U leads to a decrease in the $V_{OC,def}$.^{33,38} Figure 2c compares the E_U and V_{OC} where the gradual reduction of E_U in α -FAPI (6.10 meV) and δ -FAPI (2.77 meV) than of the c-FAPI resulted in the lower $V_{OC,def}$ and registered higher V_{OC} . From the PV measurements, we noted that the c-FAPI gave a higher performance during a reverse scan to deliver a normal hysteresis of 0.088 while the δ -FAPI and α -FAPI gave high performance under forward scans with an inverted hysteresis of -0.058 and -0.046 respectively³⁹ (Figure S12).^{38,39} The advances in the PV parameters of α -FAPI based PSCs are further established by the external quantum efficiency (EQE) and stabilized photocurrent analyses (Figure 2d and 2e) respectively. Compared to the δ -FAPI and c-FAPI, synthesized α -FAPI based PSC exhibited a higher EQE across the whole spectral region. The integrated J_{SC} was calculated

from the EQE spectra as 22.48, 22.58, and 23.20 mA cm⁻² for c-FAPI, δ -FAPI, and α -FAPI respectively which is in agreement with the J_{SC} values derived from J - V measurements and support the crystallinity improvements. For reliable reporting, we collected stabilized photocurrent under a voltage bias near the maxima power point (MPP) (Figure 2e). We propose the synthesized α -FAPbI₃ powder as a promising precursor material over the conventional and δ -FAPbI₃ powders owing to its improved PV parameters and cost-competitiveness from the employment of low-grade PbI₂.

Figure 2. Photovoltaic parameters of powder engineered PSCs: a) schematic diagram of fabricated PSC, b) J - V curve under forward bias c) relationship between E_U and corresponding V_{OC} for c-FAPI, δ -FAPI and α -FAPI films, d) EQE and integrated photocurrent spectra, and e) steady-state photocurrent measurements at maximum power point (MPP) for best-performing devices from powder engineered PSCs.

IL Additive Engineering

We realized the additive engineering with 3.5 mM EMIFAP (1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tris(pentafluoroethyl)trifluorophosphate) and HMIFAP (1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium tris(pentafluoroethyl)trifluorophosphate) with PAP anion (Figure S13) and the effect of ILs on the optoelectrical, structural and morphological properties of FAPbI₃ were monitored. As an effective

method to probe the inclusion and the molecular interactions of the PAP based ionic liquids with the α -FAPI perovskite, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) has been employed to collect the core level spectra of C 1s, N 1s, F 1s, I 3d, and Pb 4f (Figure 3, and S14-16). Figure S14 depicts the collected survey spectra for the aforementioned perovskites absorber surfaces. For the core level spectral analyses, all the elemental peaks were corrected with Aliphatic hydrocarbon (C-H/C-C) at 284.6 eV, C=O at 532 eV, and C-O peak at 533 eV, and the fitting was undertaken with a Shirley type background and Gaussian-Lorentzian (30-35% Gaussian) functions.⁴⁰ We have calculated the component compositions of deconvoluted peaks from the corresponding peak areas, and the elemental composition of perovskite surface using the equation III,⁴¹

$$C_A = \frac{I_A/S_A}{\sum_i(I_i/S_i)} \dots\dots\dots(III)$$

Where, C_A , I_A , and S_A are the required concentration, measured peak intensity and sensitivity factor of atomic species A . I_i and S_i are the peak intensity and sensitivity factor of atomic species i .

Figure 3. XPS analyses of FAPbI₃ surfaces: a) Pb 4f 1s and b) F 1s core-level spectra of α -FAPI, α -FAPI+EMIFAP, and α -FAPI+HMIFAP thin films, c, d) deconvoluted F 1s core-level spectra of c) α -FAPI+EMIFAP and d) α -FAPI+HMIFAP thin films.

The deconvoluted C 1s peaks (Figure S15 a-c) depicts, where the labeled C-H and C-N components are assigned to the aliphatic hydrocarbon and carbon bonded to nitrogen atom respectively, in FA cation. Upon EMIFAP and HMIFAP addition, three new components were emerged at 287.3, 288.96, and 292.6 eV and ascribed to imidazolium ring (N-C-N), CF₂, and CF₃ respectively.⁴² In the N 1s core-level XPS spectra (Figure S15 d-f), the peaks labeled as C-N and C=N are attributed to the FA while the Im-N peak is assigned to the imidazolium ring indicating the presence of IL cationic part.⁴³ The emerged F 1s peak (Figure 3b) suggests the inclusion of fluorine-rich anionic part of IL into the FAPbI₃ surface. The deconvoluted characteristics of

fluorine peaks exhibited the bound state of fluorine with carbon and a semi-ionic interaction with the lead (Figure 3 c,d).⁴⁴ The effect of strong F-Pb interaction was observed in the Pb core level spectra (Figure 3a). The main peaks of Pb 4f_{7/2} and 4f_{5/2} at 142.85 and 138.0 eV showed a strong shift of 0.28 and 0.42 eV towards the lower binding energy for modified α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP layers respectively.⁴⁵ In the deconvoluted peaks of pristine α -FAPbI₃ (Figure S16), besides the main peaks of Pb 4f_{5/2} and 4f_{7/2} at 142.85 and 138.0, two weak peaks at 141.9 and 137.09 eV respectively, ascribed to the metallic Pb (Pb⁰),⁴⁶ which is disappeared in modified α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP perovskite. The identified F-Pb semi-ionic interaction effectively stabilizes the under-coordinated Pb atoms at the surface. The shift of Pb²⁺ peaks towards the lower binding energy indicates the lowering of oxidation state due to the electron donation from the PAP-based EMIFAP and HMIFAP to the uncoordinated Pb²⁺ ions.⁴⁶ We observed a similar peak shift for core level spectra of I 3d (Figure S16), demonstrating the interaction between the iodide ions and PAP-based ILs that interact with the FAPbI₃ surface. To understand the F-Pb interaction in detail, we probed the elemental composition of Pb, I, and F (F-Pb component) for all the three perovskite surfaces (Table S1 and S2). We calculated the Pb:I:F ratio as 1:3.19:0, 1:3.03:0.09, and 1:2.93:0.28 for α -FAPbI₃, α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP, and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP surfaces respectively, suggesting a weakening of Pb-I interactions with increasing the F-Pb interaction. The reduced iodide content and emerged F-Pb component in F 1s core-level spectra suggest a semi-ionic F-Pb interaction inhibiting the migration of ions and passivating the surface, which enhances the PV parameters.⁴⁷

The diffractograms collected for pristine α -FAPbI₃ and ILs treated perovskite layers depict (Figure 4b), highly preferential orientation along the (h00) plane was achieved for IL treated perovskites as compared to the α -FAPbI₃. Upon the EMIFAP and HMIFAP addition, the (100) and (200) planes

were intensified and the peak intensities were drastically increased. Compared with pristine α -FAPbI₃, the diffractograms of α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP showed no peak shifts, indicating the absence of elemental substitutions. However, the FWHM of α -FAPbI₃ was decreased from 0.14° to 0.13 and 0.11° with α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP usage respectively, which implied that the addition of EMIFAP and HMIFAP ionic liquid did not alter the perovskite crystal structure but the size of crystal could be increased due to the interaction with ILs. Thus, the absence of XRD peak shift endorses the semi-ionic F-Pb interaction instead of iodide substitution as indicated by F 1s XPS core level spectral compositions. Additionally, residual peaks (PbI₂ and δ -phase peaks) were inhibited with the IL treatments. The enhanced peak intensity preferred orientation along (h00) plane and reduced FWHM infer the crystallinity enhancement.

Figure 4. Structural and optoelectronic properties of EMIFAP and HMIFAP treated α -FAPI perovskite layers: a) comparison of UV-Vis absorption spectra and b) diffractograms of α -FAPI, α -FAPI+EMIFAP, and α -FAPI+HMIFAP perovskite layers, c,d) Williamson–Hall plots for microstrain calculation for c) α -FAPI+EMIFAP, d) α -FAPI+HMIFAP perovskite layers, and e) schematic representation of microstrain induced by external stress before and after the IL treatment.

The IL treatment slows down the crystal growth and we speculate that this slow crystal growth can mitigate the external strain induced by the temperature gradients along with the bulk of FAPbI₃

thin film (Figure 4e). α -FAPI+EMIFAP and α -FAPI+HMIFAP registered significantly reduced microstrains of 1.87×10^{-4} and 1.67×10^{-4} respectively (Figure 4 c,d). We measured depth depended diffractograms for α -FAPI+HMIFAP thin film (Figure S17), and the reduced peak shifting of (100) diffraction plane in depth-profiling diffractograms suggests our hypothesis. The HMIFAP treatment mitigates the temperature gradient-induced structural inhomogeneity along with the film thickness and induces structural perfection. The efficient crystal growth was further visualized by the SEM micrographs in (Figure S18). The surface microstructure suggests that the EMIFAP and HMIFAP addition improved the uniformity and crystalline size as compared to the pristine α -FAPI. To access the effects of PAP-based ILs on the optoelectronic properties of the α -FAPI film, we collected the UV-Vis absorption spectra (Figure 4a). We observed an improved absorption onset from the α -FAPI+EMIFAP and α -FAPI+HMIFAP as compared to the α -FAPI and this can be related to the improved crystallinity. Expectedly, the calculated E_u was further dropped down to 12.98 and 12.47 meV for α -FAPI+EMIFAP and α -FAPI+EMIFAP films respectively as depicted in Figure S19. From the literature, it is evident that the PAP-based ILs show better hydrophobicity than the corresponding PF_6 and BF_4 -based ILs with the same cations.^{48,49} The hydrophobicity of PAP-based IL additives was monitored by goniometry experiments to measure the contact angle (Figure S20). For the α -FAPI a showed a value of 92° , while for the α -FAPI+EMIFAP and α -FAPI+HMIFAP added layers, it increases to 98° and 101° .

Table 1: Photovoltaic parameters of α -FAP, α -FAP+EMIFAP, and α -FAP+HMIFAP based PSC under both forward and reverse scan at a rate of 100 mV/s.

Perovskite	direction	V_{OC}	J_{SC}	FF	PCE	HI	R_s	R_{sh}
		(mV)	(mA cm ⁻²)	(%)	(%)		(Ω cm ²)	(k Ω cm ²)
α -FAP	FS	962	23.81	71.43	16.37	0.046	3.79	1.64
	RS	955	23.44	69.46	15.56		3.65	1.04
α -FAP+EMIFAP	FS	973	23.96	75.03	17.49	0.029	3.47	2.36
	RS	960	23.85	73.18	16.77		3.60	2.83
α -FAP+HMIFAP	FS	990	24.29	76.11	18.26	0.005	3.15	5.78
	RS	974	24.43	74.88	17.82		3.27	5.54

Figure 5. Photovoltaic performance and stability of EMIFAP and HMIFAP treated PSCs: a) $J-V$ characteristics under forward scan, b) EQE and integrated photocurrent of corresponding PSCs, c) normalized PCEs of α -FAP and α -FAP+HMIFAP devices (unencapsulated) normalized to initial efficiencies as a function of shelf life in a dark and ambient atmosphere with a relative humidity of 45-50%, d) stability curve of devices aged on a hot plate kept at 85 °C at ambient atmosphere

and e) MPP tracking profiles of unencapsulated devices exposed to continuous light illumination in ambient atmosphere.

The improved optoelectronic and structural properties of IL treated α -FAPbI₃ absorbers, prompt us to fabricate PSCs with α -FAPbI₃ (control device), and with α -FAPbI₃+EMIFAP, and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP. The additive engineering gave higher PV performance compare to control one, EMIFAP additive improved the PCE to 17.49% with a V_{OC} of 973 mV, J_{SC} of 23.96 mA cm⁻², and FF of 75.03% under forward scan. α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP based PSC registered a PCE of 18.26% with a boosted V_{OC} of 990 mV, J_{SC} of 24.29 mA cm⁻², and FF of 76.11% under similar conditions (Fig. 5a & Table 1). Thus, a substantial increment in the PV parameters was registered with an HMIFAP additive with a negligible hysteresis (Figure S21 and Table 1). The steady-state photocurrent measurements at maximum power points are shown (Figure S22).

The Mott–Schottky (M-S) plots of PSCs (Figure S23a-c) were measured at 10 kHz in dark to extract built-in potential (V_{bi}) and depletion width (W).^{28,50} We noted the higher build-in potential for IL-treated PSC as compared to the control device, which is in agreement with the V_{OC} enhancement. The IL-treated PSC exhibits an increased build-in potential (V_{bi}) of 1.11 V (EMIFAP) and 1.19 V (HMIFAP) and a corresponding increased depletion width (W) of 90.2 nm and 119.3 nm compared with the control α -FAPbI₃ based PSC (0.98 V and 53.9 nm) respectively. The increased depletion width allows increased charge separation and collection thus inhibit the charge recombination and leading to an enhanced photocurrent.

In addition to the increment in V_{OC} contribution from the reduced E_u , the lower series (R_s) and higher shunt resistance (R_{sh}) obtained suggest a substantial increment in the FF and V_{OC} due to reduced charge carrier recombination, which is also confirmed by dark $J-V$ measurements of IL-treated PSCs (Figure S24). The lower reverse leakage current of 4×10^{-8} mA cm⁻² and 4.28×10^{-8}

8 mA cm^{-2} were calculated for HMIFAP and EMIFAP additive based PSC while α -FAPi based PSC showed the highest leakage current of $1.45 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ which is in the agreement of its lower R_{sh} and high R_{s} value obtained from J - V measurement under illumination. (Table 1). The lower reverse saturation current density with EMIFAP and HMIFAP additive compared to that of the pristine α -FAPi, leads to higher J_{sc} , which can be attributed to the higher crystallinity in IL-treated perovskite films as indicated by UV-vis absorption and XRD spectra (Fig. 4a & b).

The statistical analysis of PV parameters for the α -FAPi, α -FAPi+EMIFAP, and α -FAPi+HMIFAP based PSCs are presented (Figure S25). Following the J - V measurements, improved EQE spectra were noted over the entire range and integrated photocurrent has been estimated as 23.2, 23.7, and 23.96 mA cm^{-2} for α -FAPi, α -FAPi+EMIFAP, and α -FAPi+HMIFAP devices respectively (Figure 5b).

Further, we investigated the stability of fabricated PSCs against the shelf life, thermal and operational stresses. Similar to α -FAPi (Figure S9-S11) it displayed superior stability, over the γ -FAPi and δ -FAPi based absorbers, under moisture and thermal stresses. Here we compared the α -FAPi based PSCs with the α -FAPi+HMIFAP. To estimate the shelf-life stability, we kept the unencapsulated devices under the dark condition at room temperature, and 45-50% RH, while for the thermal stability, the devices were annealed at 85 °C under dark and open atmosphere, and the corresponding J - V parameters were collected at regular intervals. The α -FAPi+HMIFAP based PSCs (Figure 5c) retained 85% of initial PCE after 500 hr of atmospheric exposure while the pristine α -FAPi lost its 60% of initial PCE. We noted a similar trend as of surface hydrophobicity of α -FAPi+HMIFAP (101°) than the α -FAPi (92°) (Figure S18). The pristine α -FAPi displayed excellent thermal stability (Figure S11) and with the help of additive engineering (HMIFAP treatment), it showed further improvements by retaining 90% of the initial PCE while the α -FAPi

was able to retain it 70% (Figure 5d). We attributed these merits to the higher thermal stability of PAP-based ILs and ultra-hydrophobicity. Additionally, we further monitored the operational stability of unencapsulated α -FAPbI₃ and α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP based PSCs under MPP tracking with a continuous one-sun illumination under atmospheric conditions. α -FAPbI₃+HMIFAP showed considerable stability by retaining 70% of the original PCE after 500 min where the α -FAPbI₃ lost 80% of its initial PCE within 200 min (Figure 5e). We attribute these results to the collective effect of improved interactions from hexyl-imidazolium cation with the perovskite absorber and the advanced hydrophobicity and thermal stability of the perfluoroalkyl phosphate anion.

Conclusion:

We achieved a significant decrement in the Urbach energy and microstrain through the FAPbI₃ powder engineering methodology. The synthesized α -FAPbI₃ based powder displayed an improved efficiency by minimizing the open-circuit voltage deficit. We noted that the microstrain relaxation effectively mitigated the phase instability under atmospheric conditions. Further, by employing two ultra-hydrophobic perfluoroalkyl phosphate anion-based ionic liquids as additives, the hexyl-imidazolium cationic counterpart registered the efficiency of >18% owing to reduced microstrain, Urbach energy, induced F-Pb semi-ionic interaction, and improved crystallinity. The unencapsulated device showed promising thermal and shelf-life stability along with high operational stability by retaining 70% of original PCE after 500 min of MPP tracking at atmospheric conditions.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Supporting Information is available for synthesis, characterization, and device performance.

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TOC Graphic:

